

Global assessment of population exposure to multiple climate-related hazards from 2003 to 2021: a retrospective analysis

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Summary

Background The climate crisis is increasingly recognised as a health crisis, driven in part by the growing frequency and intensity of climate-related hazards, such as heatwaves and wildfires. These hazards can coincide, potentially leading to compound impacts. However, little is known about where and how often such combinations occur globally. This study aims to map historical population exposure to multiple interacting climate-related hazards and identify regions that have been most affected.

Methods In this retrospective study, we analysed global data from the 2024 *Lancet* Countdown on health and climate change, International Best Track Archive for Climate Stewardship, The Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project, and WorldPop from 2003 to 2021 at a 0.25° resolution to examine the population that was exposed to combinations of six climate hazards: heatwaves, droughts, wildfires (PM_{2.5}), extreme precipitation, river floods, and tropical cyclones. We identified administrative level 1 regions based on several hotspot definitions and did detailed case studies in the most exposed regions.

Findings We detail how frequently people at each grid point have been exposed to various combinations of hazards, revealing both regular patterns and rare, region-specific occurrences. Our analysis indicates an increase in per-person exposure to many hazards during the study period, with a more pronounced rise in multihazard exposure than single-hazards. Between 2003–12 and 2012–21, per-person exposure to three or more hazards increased by 69%. Heatwaves were the most common hazard and also showed the clearest trend, largely driving the observed increases in both single-hazard and multihazard exposure. Multihazard hotspots vary depending on the specific definition used. For instance, exposure to multiple hazards is explained by the seasonality of hazards, which leads them to co-occur in the same months. Additionally, incorporating specific vulnerable age groups into our analysis reveals hotspots that consider the sociodemographic characteristics of the regions.

Interpretation These findings highlight the importance of incorporating multihazards into climate and health risk assessments. Our study enables an examination of historical events to deepen our understanding of interactions between hazards. Given the rarity of many hazard combinations, traditional epidemiological methods might fall short. Thus, alternative approaches, such as storyline development, are essential to enhance our preparation for future multihazard occurrences. This work finally serves as a crucial baseline future multihazard risk assessment under different climate and socioeconomic scenarios.

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Introduction

Climate change has been named the greatest global threat to human health in the 21st century,¹ as it affects a wide array of health determinants. The most direct consequence is through unprecedented heatwaves, prompting the UN Secretary-General to call for urgent global action in July, 2024, to protect vulnerable populations and workers from extreme temperatures.² Many other health impacts have been observed, including reduced water availability and food production in some areas due to droughts and poor air quality resulting from wildfires.³ In response to

these growing threats, many countries and global organisations have increased their efforts to assess and plan for climate-related health risks.⁴ Initiatives such as the 2024 *Lancet* Countdown on health and climate change have brought sustained attention to the health impacts of climate change at a global level,³ and the topic has gained prominence at recent UN Climate Conferences, including in 2023 and 2024.

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, climate risk is defined as the probability multiplied by the severity (ie, impact) of an extreme climate event

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Research in context

Evidence before this study

In the past few years, more attention has been directed towards the impacts of climate-related hazards on health. Yet, these hazards have largely been analysed in isolation, without considering their potential interactions. However, such interactions could lead to compounding effects. For example, it has been observed that wildfires and heat together can result in higher mortality rates than either hazard occurring alone. Despite this, the effects of most combinations of hazards are not well understood. We searched PubMed, Web of Science, and Google Scholar for studies published between Jan 1, 2000, and March 31, 2025, combining terms such as “compound events” or “multihazard” with “population” or “health” (full list of search terms is in the appendix p 1). We found no comprehensive global assessments quantifying population exposure to more than two hazards simultaneously; existing studies were mostly at regional or country scale or focused on specific hazard pairs.

Added value of this study

The main contribution of this study is its ability to identify past population exposure to combinations of climate-related hazards.

With globally consistent data from 2003 to 2021, this research integrates multiple climate-related health hazards into a comprehensive analysis. This approach is novel in its examination of the geographical and temporal patterns of hazard co-occurrence, offering detailed insights into the regions and periods in which multihazards have historically led to substantial population exposure.

Implications of all the available evidence

The findings from this study emphasise the need for health systems to adapt to the complexities of multiple simultaneous climate-related hazards. Understanding where and when these hazards overlap allows policy makers and health practitioners to better allocate resources and design interventions to mitigate health impacts. Additionally, by identifying historical hotspots of multihazards, this study enables researchers to orient future studies towards analysing the past effects of these events. Our findings also serve as a baseline for future research to project the exposure to these combinations of hazards under varying climate and socioeconomic scenarios.

See Online for appendix

computed as a function of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability.⁵ Hazards refer to potentially harmful climate-related events, either acute (eg, heatwaves or floods) or chronic (eg, persistent droughts), that occur with a certain probability. Exposure describes the presence of people, infrastructure, or ecosystems in hazard-prone areas, and vulnerability encompasses the social, economic, and health-related factors that influence susceptibility to harm.

Although considerable progress has been made in assessing individual hazards and their health impacts, these events often occur in combination or succession, which can significantly amplify impacts.^{6,7} WHO has highlighted the importance of compound events for the resilience of health systems,⁸ yet these interactions are still rarely considered in health and climate assessments. For instance, in the *Lancet* Countdown, different hazards are assessed separately, ignoring their interplay.

Zscheischler and colleagues brought the concept of compound events to the forefront of climate science and proposed a typology comprising two broad categories: co-occurring and successive events.⁷ Based on this classification, several studies have assessed population exposure to compound events using two or three climate variables.^{9–11} In disaster risk research, the term multihazard is more commonly used to describe a similar concept, and can also include non-climatic hazards.¹² For instance, in the Hindu Kush Himalaya region, high-resolution models have been applied to estimate population exposure to multihazard floods, wildfires, and landslide events.¹³

Despite these efforts, the full scope of compounding or multihazard events often remains obscured, even after they occur. It is challenging to disentangle the effects of multiple

interacting hazards, leading to oversimplified attributions to a dominant hazard. For instance, in 2010, an extraordinary heatwave in eastern Europe was coupled with severe wildfires that degraded air quality. A study estimated that of the 11 000 excess deaths in Moscow, around 2000 were caused by the interaction of poor air quality and heat.¹⁴ Such interactions have been analysed in a few previous studies for a small subset of hazard combinations and events, but the contribution of multiple co-occurring hazards in past events remains largely unknown.

Assessing the effects of interacting hazards requires consistent and comparable datasets. Yet, climate and health research remains fragmented, and methodologies are often inconsistent.¹⁵ We first aimed to assess the global population exposure to each hazard combination from 2003 to 2021, accounting for population growth and a counterfactual scenario without population growth. We then aimed to identify six hotspot regions at the administrative 1 level (first subnational administrative division—eg, states, provinces, or regions, depending on the country), selected based on characteristics such as the co-occurrence of multiple hazards and the presence of vulnerable populations. Based on the timelines of single-hazard occurrences, we aimed to examine the seasonality of hazard co-occurrence in these regions. Because we refer to the co-occurrence of hazards, which are often more complex than individual climate variables, we use the term multihazard.

Methods

Study design and hazard parameters

In this study, we take a spatially explicit approach, linking monthly climate-related hazard data to gridded population

data to quantify population exposure to single and multiple hazards globally.

WHO identifies six categories of hazards linked to negative health outcomes when combined with vulnerability: extreme weather events, heat stress, air quality, water quality and quantity, food security, and vector distribution and ecology.⁴ The *Lancet* Countdown data platform provides indicators for monitoring some of these hazards, which we used when available. However, not all hazards recommended by WHO for adaptation plans are covered by the *Lancet* Countdown or could be included in our analysis. Specifically, hazards related to vector distribution are not included in our analysis and aspects of food and water security are only indirectly considered.

We focus on six hazards from 2003 to 2021: heatwaves, droughts, river floods, extreme precipitation, tropical cyclones, and wildfires (PM_{2.5}). The computation of these hazard data primarily required standard climatic variables, such as temperature or precipitation. Exceptions include the wildfires (via PM_{2.5}) indicator, which relies on satellite data, and tropical cyclones data derived from observational storm tracks in the International Best Track Archive for Climate Stewardship.¹⁶ The limitation of satellite data availability for wildfires (PM_{2.5}), which begins only in 2003, sets the temporal bounds of our study.

Definitions of the hazard, data sources, possible exposure values, and typical health effects are detailed in the appendix (p 3). Most of the hazards included in this study are acute (eg, heatwaves, wildfires, tropical cyclones, and extreme precipitations). However, drought can be either acute or chronic; here, it is treated as chronic, defined by conditions persisting for at least 6 months.

Population

We used the WorldPop unconstrained global mosaic dataset, including age-specific data for people older than 65 years and younger than 5 years, covering the period 2003–21, with one value per grid point per year. The original WorldPop data are provided on a 1 km × 1 km grid. We upscaled these data to the ERA5 0.25° grid by assigning each 1 km cell to its nearest neighbour and summing the population within each resulting grid point.

Population exposure to single hazards and multihazards

We estimated monthly population exposure to climate-related hazards at the 0.25° grid-cell level with CLIMADA (version 6.0.1). For binary hazards, such as heatwaves, wildfires, droughts, and tropical cyclones, we recorded exposure if at least one event occurred within the month. For hazards with subgrid variability, such as river floods and extreme precipitations, we calculated exposure of population based on the proportion of the grid cell affected and retained the maximum value recorded within the month.

Figure 1 illustrates how population exposure is assessed based on three hazards and how multihazard exposure is determined. Individuals exposed to multiple hazards

Figure 1: Schematic representation of multihazard exposure for heatwaves, river floods, and tropical cyclones

Although heatwaves and tropical cyclones are binary and affect the entire grid cell, river floods can affect only a portion of the grid cell, as illustrated.

within the same month were only counted once in the total exposed population. A more detailed explanation of the methodology is provided in the appendix (p 4).

Identification of hotspots

We aggregated exposures at the administrative level 1 to define hotspots, as this provides a globally consistent unit for comparison while maintaining subnational detail. Administrative level 1 regions are widely used in policy and disaster response planning, making them relevant for assessing multihazard exposure. We used the administrative level 1 borders as defined by the geoBoundaries project.¹⁷ Small (<500 km²) administrative level 1 regions were not considered in the analysis, as they might not contain population grid points at the resolution of our data.

There are various ways to define hotspots, each emphasising different aspects of the exposure to hazards. In our analysis, we consider both the absolute number of individuals exposed and the relative proportion of the population affected in each administrative region. Additionally, we account for one aspect of vulnerability by considering age-specific exposure. All hotspot definitions are computed as the mean monthly exposure to hazards, meaning that total exposure to hazards is aggregated over all months in the study period and then divided by the number of months. For the multihazard hotspot definitions, we use a threshold of three or more hazards. This threshold balances the need for considering multiple hazards while keeping a large

For the WorldPop dataset see <https://hub.worldpop.org/geodata/listing?id=65>

For the CLIMADA software see <https://zenodo.org/records/15020318>

Panel: Hotspot definitions**Absolute single-hazard hotspot**

The mean number of individuals in a region exposed to at least one hazard per month.

Relative single-hazard hotspot

The mean proportion of the total population in a region exposed to at least one hazard per month.

Absolute multihazard hotspot

The mean number of individuals in a region exposed to at least three hazards within the same month.

Relative multihazard hotspot

The mean proportion of the total population in a region exposed to at least three hazards within the same month.

Relative vulnerable population multihazard hotspot (<5 years)

The mean number of children younger than 5 years in a region exposed to at least three hazards within the same month, relative to the total population.

Relative vulnerable population multihazard hotspot (>65 years)

The mean number of adults older than 65 years in a region exposed to at least three hazards within the same month, relative to the total population.

coverage. Any other hotspots can easily be considered if desired.

We use the term hotspot to explore regions with concentrated population exposure, but this does not imply severity of effects. Rather, each definition offers a different perspective on where and how people might be exposed and should not be interpreted as a direct measure of risk or health outcomes.

The hotspot definitions used in this study are listed in the panel.

Further methodological details for the hotspot definitions are provided in the appendix (pp 5–6).

Role of the funding source

The funding sources had no role in the design of the study, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, writing of the manuscript, or the decision to submit for publication.

Results

Heatwaves are the hazard with the greatest mean number of months during which people have been exposed during the 2003–21 period (appendix p 9). This prevalence is also reflected in the frequent co-occurrence of heatwaves with other hazards across the globe (figure 2), making heatwave combinations a key focus in multihazard exposure analysis. People in the northern hemisphere have generally been more exposed to heatwaves than in the southern hemisphere. Children younger than 5 years have been exposed to a mean of 17 months, whereas individuals older than 65 years have been exposed to a mean of 20 months (appendix p 9).

In the case of wildfires, children younger than 5 years have been exposed to a mean of 0·9 months of wildfires globally, whereas individuals older than 65 years have been exposed to a mean of 0·6 months (appendix p 9).

People have also been exposed to the combination of heatwaves and wildfires, mainly in South America, western North America, and Russia. When a third hazard is considered, the most common three-hazard combination is droughts, heatwaves, and wildfires. In these same regions, fewer grid points have had this three-hazard combination, but it remains widespread. The population of people older than 65 years have been more frequently exposed to both the heatwaves and wildfires combination and the drought, heatwaves, and wildfires combination compared with children younger than 5 years and the general population. This trend is also observed for exposure to any combination of three or more hazards (appendix p 9).

Although we observed a clear seasonality and yearly recurrence in heatwave exposure globally (figure 3), and to a lesser extent to wildfires (PM_{2.5}), exposure to combinations of hazards happened only in some years (appendix p 10).

We observed an effect of population growth (appendix p 10); for instance, 29% more people were exposed in the most severe month for three or more hazards when considering population growth.

To communicate changes with more certainty, longer observation periods will be required. But for some hazards (eg, heatwaves and combinations with heatwaves) an increase can be observed (figure 3), even without considering population growth. Comparing 2012–21 with 2003–12, the mean exposure per person to one or more hazards increased by 17·6% (95% CI 2·1–34·5). Exposure to two or more hazards increased by 29·4% (2·4–69·4), and exposure to three or more hazards, although still rare, increased by 69·0% (12·1–145·7; appendix p 9). These increases in exposure to hazards can be observed throughout most of the world (appendix p 8). When excluding heatwaves, the trends across age groups became conflicting, suggesting that the overall patterns are largely driven by the strong signal from heatwave exposure and

Figure 2: Number of months during which people in each grid point have been exposed to a hazard or combination of hazards

The hazards shown are heatwaves (A); heatwaves and droughts (B); heatwaves and wildfires (C); drought, heatwaves, and wildfires (D); one or more hazards of any category (E); or three or more hazards of any category (F). Data are for the years 2003–21 (228 months total). The colour bar starts at 1 month. Grey means the combination did not occur or no population was exposed. The grey land background does not include very small islands, which are nonetheless captured by the data grid and appear in the overlaid colours.

that longer time series are needed to discern clearer trends in the exposure to other combinations of hazards.

The hotspots highlight different facets of hazard exposure and are not evenly distributed across the globe (figure 4). In absolute numbers, the highly populated areas in India and China are most heavily exposed to singular hazards, whereas when mapped relative to the total population, most of the world is exposed. When considering at least three simultaneous hazards, north-east China and the west coast of the USA emerge as highly exposed in absolute terms, whereas when mapped in relative terms, northern regions in Russia and Canada, as well as in the Amazon basin and Indonesia, stand out. In these relative population maps, some regions, such as northern Russia and Canada, appear

particularly prominent due to the large spatial size of their administrative units. Although the total exposed population might be relatively small and concentrated in urban areas, the entire region is represented as affected in the relative metric. For the vulnerable populations of people younger than 5 years and older than 65 years, the pattern also shows high exposure in northern Russia, Canada, the Amazon basin, and Indonesia, with additionally notable local hotspots such as Madagascar for the people younger than 5 years and Japan for people older than 65 years.

The overall multihazard situation is more nuanced when also considering the different seasonality of hazards per region. For each of the six hotspot definitions, we show the monthly exposures to all hazards in one hotspot for each

Figure 3: Time series of the number of people exposed per month globally for a subset of hazards or combination of hazards

The hazards shown are heatwaves (A); heatwaves and droughts (B); heatwaves and wildfires (C); drought, heatwaves, and wildfires (D); one or more hazards of any category (E); or three or more hazards of any category (F). The plots are differentiated based on whether population growth is considered or population is fixed at 2003 levels. The dates of the three most severe months globally are indicated for each combination.

definition (figure 5). These hotspots are Uttar Pradesh (India), Kwango (Democratic Republic of the Congo), Jiangsu Province (China), Alto Paraguay (Paraguay), Darkhan-Uul (Mongolia), and Wakayama Prefecture (Japan). These are the regions with the highest risk scores for the six definitions, except for Darkhan-Uul. The definition for the relative vulnerable population (<5 years) multihazard hotspot results in Alto Paraguay being the hotspot a second time; however, Darkhan-Uul was chosen here as it is in the top ten hotspots for this definition and allows to cover another set of hazard combinations.

For instance, figure 5 shows that in Kwango (Democratic Republic of the Congo), although there is a clear seasonality for wildfires, the other hazards occur at different times throughout the year. Hence there is a high exposure to single hazards but not to multiple hazards within a month. However, in Wakayama (Japan), heatwaves, tropical cyclone winds, and extreme precipitations tend to all only

happen in the summer months, explaining the high exposure to three hazards.

Figure 6 showcases the most severe months that have occurred in each of the hotspot shown in figure 5, based on the different definitions. Generally, the multihazard nature of these events was reported (in the news or literature), but with little details on their specific effects on people. A qualitative summary of the events is given in the appendix (pp 12–13). The poor understanding of the effects of multihazard events on exposed populations might stem from the complex geographical distribution and localised nature of compounding hazards. For instance, the event in Darkhan-Uul included two distinct hazard combinations in the administrative level 1 region itself, and more than 12 different ones in the larger region around it. This complex geographical interaction is because some hazards tend to have large geographical extents, such as heatwaves, droughts, tropical cyclones, and wildfires (PM_{2.5}), whereas others, such as river floods, are

Figure 4: Multiple administrative level 1 hotspot maps based on the risk scores

(A) Regions with the highest burden of exposure to single hazards highlighted, considering the number of people and the number of months exposed. (B) Regions with the highest burden of exposure to single hazards highlighted, relative to the total population of the level. (C) Regions with the highest burden of exposure to three or more hazards, considering the number of people and the number of months exposed. (D) Regions with the highest burden of exposure to three or more hazards, relative to the total population of the level. (E) Regions with the highest burden of exposure to three or more hazards of the population younger than 5 years, relative to the total population of the level. (F) Regions with the highest burden of exposure to three or more hazards of the population older than 65 years, relative to the total population of the level. The results of each hotspot are normalised between 0 and 1 but are here simply described on a scale from low to high.

more localised, with many different combinations occurring in a small area. Even in Uttar Pradesh and Kwango, which were chosen because they had the highest number of people exposed to one or more hazards, the hazards do not occur in isolation.

Discussion

In this study, we integrated multiple climate-related hazards to estimate monthly population exposures from

2003 to 2021. We quantified how often people at each grid point were exposed to hazard combinations, revealing both recurring patterns and rare regional events. Our approach allows us to revisit historical events, analyse the array of climate hazards present, and further study how these interactions affected people's health. Our study shows how global data—such as those produced by the *Lancet Countdown*—can be used to assess the past co-occurrence

Figure 5: Seasonality of the percentage of people exposed to extreme weather events in the hotspot administrative levels 1
 The hotspots shown are Uttar Pradesh in India (A), Kwango in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (B), Jiangsu Province in China (C), Alto Paraguay in Paraguay (D), Darkhan-Uul in Mongolia (E), and Wakayama Prefecture in Japan (F). The bold lines show the median across the 19 years and transparent colour shows the 90th percentile range. Note that no visible bold line means that the median is 0 for all months. Wildfires (PM_{2.5}), heatwaves, droughts, tropical cyclones and extreme precipitations are shown together in a graph, whereas river floods are shown in a separate frame with a separate y-axis as it generally affects a smaller share of the population. Note the scale of the y axes differ throughout the figure.

of climate-related health hazards (ie, heatwaves, droughts, wildfires [PM_{2.5}], and extreme precipitations), alongside river floods and tropical cyclones.

To our knowledge, this is the first study to assess the co-occurrence of multiple climate-related health hazards at the global scale and with subannual time resolution. Our analysis provides a globally consistent multihazard

perspective across several climate-related hazards, with an explicit focus on health-relevant exposures. Our findings show that the phenomenon of hazards rarely occurring in isolation is not only widespread but also increasing over time. As climate change accelerates, understanding how these hazards interact and compound will be essential for anticipating future risks and informing adaptation.

Figure 6: Events with the most people exposed in the highlighted administrative level 1 regions

The hotspots shown are Uttar Pradesh, India, in June, 2005 (A); Kwango, Democratic Republic of the Congo, in June, 2010 (B); Jiangsu Province, China, in July, 2016 (C); Alto Paraguay, Paraguay, in October, 2007 (D); Darkhan-Uul, Mongolia, in August, 2015 (E); and Wakayama Prefecture, Japan, in August, 2003 (F). These hotspots were identified through different definitions. For the two first definitions, these are the months in which most people have been exposed to one or more hazards, whereas for the other they are the months in which most people have been exposed to three or more hazards. The hotspot administrative level 1 regions are highlighted in black, and we show the hazard exposure for a wider bounding box. Note that grid points represent aggregated exposure data, and due to the resolution, some can appear over water bodies, particularly near coastlines. DR=drought. EP=extreme precipitation. HW=heatwave. RF=river floods. TC=tropical cyclone. WF=wildfire.

Our study can support epidemiological⁶ and clinical¹⁸ research towards improved understanding of the health effects of multihazard events. A recent editorial similarly underscored the importance of predictive modelling explicitly tailored to compound hazard scenarios within a cardiological context.¹⁸ However, our analysis highlights that some multihazard occurrences might be historically rare or unprecedented, constraining the capability of models to predict the specific human health consequences. In such situations, alternative approaches, including counterfactual scenario analyses,¹⁹ analogues drawn from similar regions, and climate–health stress tests based on hypothetical yet plausible scenarios,²⁰ can provide insights into possible consequences. The previously mentioned editorial emphasises complementary measures that can be effectively implemented even in the absence of precise predictions of health outcomes, such as training health-care practitioners, investing in climate-resilient infrastructure, and enhancing surveillance systems and strengthening interagency coordination.

Beyond current effects, it is equally important to anticipate how multihazard events could evolve under future climate conditions. Our data show an increasing exposure to several single hazards, with a more pronounced rise in multihazard exposure. Our study prepares the way for future multihazard risk projections under various climate scenarios. Although most hazards can be modelled with standard climate variables, wildfires (PM_{2.5}) require satellite-based estimates, as they depend on vegetation and human activity. However, recent efforts have quantified changes in wildfire smoke globally under different climate scenarios and could be used for this purpose.²¹ Similarly, river floods and tropical cyclones demand additional modelling layers to capture their dynamics. The ISIMIP project²² supports such studies by providing hazard data and a representative subset of CMIP6 models, enabling large-scale multihazard projections.¹²

Our analysis reveals how different regions emerge as hotspots based on different criteria, each highlighting distinct factors of population exposure to hazards. We define the risk scores based on both overall population exposure to single hazards and multihazards to highlight regions where multiple climate-related hazards coincide and could challenge local health systems, especially in multihazard scenarios. Correspondingly, per-person exposure reveals areas where large portions of the population could be exposed to one or more hazards within a month, putting local capacities at risk of being overwhelmed, although external intervention might be easier. By also considering vulnerable age groups, the analysis shows how the situation changes when absolute and relative exposure, multihazards, and demographic aspects are integrated, showing that some areas could be overlooked if these interacting factors are not accounted for.

Further focusing on these hotspot regions, an overview of hazard seasonality helps explain why some areas are disproportionately affected by multihazards in our model.

In some regions, hazards co-occur during specific periods, whereas in others (eg, Kwango) multiple hazards occur throughout the year but do not necessarily overlap within the same month due to the absence of a common seasonality. This finding highlights how methodological choices, such as analysing monthly co-occurrence rather than annual co-occurrence, can influence which regions are identified as hotspots. Although our focus on a monthly resolution supports short-term health system responses by identifying periods of concurrent hazards, broader perspectives based on annual or cumulative exposure could also be important for understanding longer-term health outcomes. These insights can be further strengthened by integrating information on hazard–disease associations. For example, Mora and colleagues provide a global overview of which diseases are linked to specific types of extreme weather, which could help identify when and where populations face compounding risks to health.²³

Building on these insights, this study represents an important step in evaluating the co-occurrence of climate-related health hazards. As climate change progresses, hazards will not only become more frequent and severe but will also increasingly overlap, as shifting climate patterns alter the seasonality and distribution of extreme events. As a result, populations are likely to face more multihazard conditions, making it imperative to understand the consequences of these overlaps and improve the modelling of hazard interactions, including changing seasonal patterns and emerging combinations of hazards under climate change.

Although our study offers a consistent global framework for assessing multihazard exposure, it comes with some limitations. First, the spatial resolution of 0.25° constrains precision, particularly in large grid cells where binary hazard thresholds (eg, for heatwaves and droughts) might overestimate exposure by assuming the entire population is affected. For fractional hazards, such as floods and extreme precipitation, exposure is based on the affected area but could miss mismatches in the spatial overlap of hazards. Second, our analysis relies on monthly data. Although daily or weekly resolutions are common in epidemiological studies, the monthly timescale supports comparability across hazards and aligns with the timeframes in which health systems often respond to compounding events. Finer temporal resolutions would be valuable for localised or disease-specific studies. Third, we use fixed intensity thresholds that might not reflect regional vulnerability. Tailoring these thresholds or integrating probabilistic models could refine exposure estimates. Similarly, incorporating region-specific hazard–health relationships would enhance the utility of the framework. Fourth, our analysis focuses on exposure and does not account for vulnerability factors such as health-care access, socioeconomic status, or infrastructure resilience. Future work could integrate such indicators and additional climate-sensitive hazards such as vector-borne disease risk.

Overall, the framework developed here serves as a crucial baseline for future studies assessing how climate change and demographic shifts will shape multihazard risk.

By providing a systematic approach to quantifying past multihazard exposure, this study enables researchers to track how these interactions evolve throughout time and explore future scenarios. The data and methods presented here equip policy makers and researchers with tools to retrospectively analyse multihazard exposures and develop strategies to mitigate the risks posed by increasingly complex climate-driven health threats.

Contributors

ZS was responsible for data curation, formal analysis, and writing the original draft. MCdR, DNB, and CMK contributed to the conceptualisation and study design of the project and provided supervision and guidance throughout the project. ZS and CMK verified the underlying data. FJC-G and NS were involved in supervision and participated in the review and editing of the manuscript. SZ handled data curation specifically for river flood data and contributed to writing by reviewing and editing. JC curated the data for heatmap analysis and participated in writing by reviewing and editing the manuscript. All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript. All authors had full access to all the data in the study and accept responsibility for the decision to submit for publication.

Declaration of interests

We declare no competing interests.

Data sharing

A frozen version of the code used is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16275756>. The population exposure to the single hazards for the three age categories is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15726528>.

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